

**Citation for the Presentation of the 2018
ICPE Medal to**

**Professor Marisa Michelini
Italy**

**at GIREP-ICPE-EPEC-MPTL 2019
Budapest
July 2019**

Marisa Michelini is full professor in Physics Education at Udine University, Italy, where she has been Rector delegate for Didactic and Innovation, Tutoring and School-University Relationships since 1994. She founded and led many institutional structures (CIRD, CLDF, CORT, FASF, SSIS, including first Italian PhD in Physics Education Research) and developed rules for evaluation, didactic management and innovation. She has been responsible for the Research Unit in Physics Education (URDF) since 1992.

*Prof. Marisa Michelini receiving her award
from Prof. Roberto Nardi, Chair of ICPE*

Professor Michelini is president of GIREP, director of the Italian University Consortium GEO, committee member of the Multimedia Physics Teaching and Learning (MPTL), board member of EPS-PED division and honorary member of the Italian Association for Physics Teaching (AIF), after serving in the Executive Committee of ESERA.

Her research activity is in two fields: Electrical transport properties in thin films and, Physics Education, with continuity from 1976, having research responsibility for the following:

- a) Curricular Research to build vertical paths and study learning progression. Educational paths on thermal and optical phenomena, study of motion, electromagnetism, quantum mechanics and superconductivity.
- b) Design Based Research to study ways to overcome learning knots and the role of ICT in learning processes.
- c) Empirical research on learning processes and developing formal thinking.
- d) Innovation in physics teaching and learning and developing original proposals for lab activities integrated in vertical paths.
- e) Informal learning, Inquiry Based Learning, and CLOE-Conceptual Labs for Operative Exploration in bridging common sense ideas with scientific ones.
- f) Teacher Education.
- g) Models for school-university cooperation and institutional ways for co-planning instruction and relative supports.
- h) Innovation in University Strategies and Education.

She was responsible for two European Union (EU) Projects on physics education and partner in five other EU Projects. She also carried out 46 projects on physics and teacher education at the national level as the scientist responsible for Italy and was responsible for eight projects at the regional level. She has been head of the Italian series Projects

(IDIFO) since 2006, involving 20 Universities and INFN for the Innovation in Physics Teaching and guidance on modern physics. She has been Director of eight biannual Master's programs and seven specialization courses focused on teacher education.

She has organized 9 International Congresses and 8 National relevant congresses and schools, being on the Advisory board of all GIREP, ICPE, MPTL Congress organizations in the last 15 years. She has been a Keynote (invited) speaker at 28 international Congresses (AAPT, GIREP, EPS, IACPE, ICPE, LAPEN, LASERA, MPTL) and at 39 National Congresses.

Professor Michelini's work is documented in more than 660 refereed publications, books and journals, 257 of which are in English.

*Prof. Marisa Michelini (Italy) – ICPE Medal 2018 and Roberto Nardi (Brazil) – ICPE Chair.
Among members of the Organizing Committee (Csaba Sükösd and Beáta Jarosietvitz – left) and
ICPE commissioners: from left: Naoshi Takahashi (Japan), Zulma Gangoso (Argentina), David
Sokoloff (U.S.A.), Tetyana Antimirova (Canada) and Dean Zollman (U.S.A.).*

Roberto Nardi
ICPE Chair